

HEAT POLYMERISATION OF OILS

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Polymerisation of some of indigenous vegetable oils : safflower, niger seed and olive oils, has been studied with reference to cracking. The nature of the polymerised products and the acids of the lower molecular weights have been identified.

The subject of heat polymerisation has been studied by several workers (Wolf, *Fette. Chem. Umschau*, 1933, **40**, 113; Steger and Van Loon, *ibid.*, 1935, **42**, 217; Kino, *Sci. papers Inst. Phys. Chem. Res. Tokyo*, 1931, **16**, 127, 132, *et. seq.*; Morell, *Chem. Ind.*, 1937, **73**, 1087; Kurz, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1935, **48**, 3; Scheiber, *Fette. u. Seifen*, 1936, **43**, 103; Kienle, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1936, **55**, 229; Bradley, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1937, **29**, 440, *et. seq.*). These workers have studied the heat polymerisation by heating the oils at about 300° in presence of an inert gas to avoid oxidation. The progress of polymerisation was followed by determining the iodine value, refractive index, etc., the polymerised products were found to be far too complex for direct identification and therefore it has not been possible so far to establish any theory which accounts completely for the mechanism of polymerisation. However, it has been indicated that in the polymerisation the first stage is the cracking of the fatty acids at the point of the double bonds in the unsaturated acids; but no attempt has been made by previous workers to identify these products of cracking. Such an identification would lead to a better understanding of the mechanism of polymerisation.

We therefore intended to study the polymerisation of Indian vegetable oils and to study the nature of the products of cracking, as well as that of the polymerised products.

Safflower, niger seed and olive oils were chosen for this study because

- (1) The component glycerides of these oils are known :
- (2) Safflower and niger seed oils represent a typical class of oils containing linolic acid while olive oil represents another class containing oleic acid as the major component acids.

The heat polymerisation of these oils therefore will give an idea of the polymerisation of the glycerides of oleic and linolic acids. Simultaneously with this work the effect of heat on pure simple glycerides has also been studied as it will make the interpretation of these facts easier (Phalnikar and Bhidé, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1943, **11**, Part V, p. 77).

EXPERIMENTAL

The Physical Properties of the Oils.—Safflower and Niger seed oils used in this work were extracted by pressing the seeds (purchased from the local market, Poona district) in a country *Ghanees*. The olive oil used was a commercial sample available in the local market. These had the following physical and chemical constants.

TABLE I

Constant.	Safflower.	Niger.	Olive.
Refractive index at 30°	1.47287	1.46720 at 26°	1.46391.
Density	0.9669	0.9202	0.9170
Iodine value (I.V.) (Rosemund and Kuhnemmi)	125.4	120.5	88.0
Saponification value (S. V.)	188.1	193.5	189.0
Acid value (A. V.)	2.439	2.0	1.0

Polymerisation of the Oils.—The oils were heated in a distilling flask with a naked flame under reduced pressure, the temperature of the oil being 360°-400°. The volatile liquid

products were condensed (distillate). Some CO_2 and a large amount of acrolein were evolved. The heating of the oils was discontinued as soon as frothing begun to occur. The residue and the distillate were then analysed separately.

Methods of Analysis.—The distillate was separated into a neutral portion and an acid portion. The neutral portion was further separated into saponifiable and non-saponifiable portions. The saponifiable part was found to be an ester of oleic acid. The non-saponifiable part consisted mainly of saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons with traces of ketones and alcohols. The probable constitution of the hydrocarbons was determined by oxidation and molecular weight determination. The acids of the acid portion were converted into methyl esters and fractionally distilled. The major portion of this distillate consisted of mixtures of acids (saturated and unsaturated) with less than twelve carbon atoms, and a small portion (high boiling) consisted mainly of the esters of oleic acid and acids of higher molecular weights. These high molecular weight acids (polymerised acids) could not be separated into homogeneous products by the usual methods of separation *viz.*, as lead and magnesium salts etc.

Analysis of the Residue.—The residue was saponified. The acids obtained were converted into methyl esters, fractionally distilled and the acids obtained from various fractions were found to be complex mixtures. Attempts were made to separate these complex mixtures into individual homogeneous acids by lead salt and magnesium salt methods but homogeneous products could not be obtained. The molecular weight and equivalent weight determinations show that the acids were monobasic and dibasic acids. Some of them contained a hydroxylic group also as shown by the acetyl value.

For the sake of brevity the analytical constants and other details have not been given. A summary of the results obtained has been given below.

Safflower Oil

The oil (500 g.) on distillation gave 80 g. of the distillate (16%), 400 g. of the residue (80%) and 20 g. of the gases—(4% by difference).

Myristic, palmitic, stearic and arachidic acids were identified in the solid acids of the distillate, while heptylic, pelargonic acids and an acid of equivalent weight 398.8 were the saturated acids (liquid) and oleic acid and an acid with 10 carbon atoms with a double bond at the fourth carbon atom were the unsaturated acids which were identified in the liquid acid portion of the distillate. From the saponifiable part of the neutral portion of the distillate, oleic acid was identified, thus showing that the saponifiable part of the neutral portion was some ester of oleic acid. In the unsaponifiable portion of the neutral fraction of the distillate, ketones, alcohols probably hydrocarbons of different molecular weights were found to be present.

The Residue.—The highly viscous residue on hydrolysis and subsequent fractionation of the methyl esters of the acids showed that most of the acids originally present in the oil were also present and in addition, acids of high molecular weights ranging from 380-584 were also found. Attempts to obtain homogeneous polymerised acids failed. Oxidation also did not give any definite result. These polymerised acids also possessed an acetyl value and are probably hydroxy unsaturated acids. This is in agreement with the views of Kurz *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1936, 49, 235). Some of these acids are monomeric and others dimeric. The nature of these acids appear to be similar to that of polymerised acids investigated by Bradley and co-workers (*loc. cit.*). Their stability to oxidation indicated the possibility of their being ring

compounds. This view is supported by the work of Farmer (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1940.), who has isolated six-membered ring compounds from the polymerisation of methyl sorbate.

Niger Seed Oil

Niger seed and olive oils have been similarly subjected to heat polymerisation. In each case the distillate and the residue were analysed as described above. The residue in the case of niger seed oil was first resolved into two fractions by acetone into an acetone-soluble part and the other, an acetone-insoluble part. Each portion was analysed separately as above. The results in both the cases were similar to those obtained above, hence for the sake of brevity details of identification have been omitted and the results are described briefly below.

Heat polymerisation of Niger seed Oil.—1150 G. of the oil on distillation at reduced pressure gave 287 g. (24.6%) of the distillate, 750 g. (65.3%) of the residue and 113 g. of gases (9.8% by difference).

Composition of the Distillate.—The distillate was separated into neutral portion and acid portion. The neutral portion consisted of a glyceride of oleic acid and a mixture of ketones and alcohols and probably hydrocarbons of different molecular weights. The acidic portion of the distillate was separated into solid and liquid acids. The solid acids identified were lauric, myristic, palmitic, stearic and traces of arachidic acids. The original oil also contains these solid acids. Caprylic acid accompanied by lauric, myristic and palmitic acids forms the major part of the "liquid" acids. Oleic acid and an acid with one double bond, probably at the fourth carbon atom, have been identified in the liquid unsaturated acids.

The Residue.—The brown and viscous residue was separated into acetone-soluble and acetone-insoluble parts. Both these parts were hydrolysed and the acids obtained were converted into methyl esters. The lower boiling fraction showed practically the same composition as that of the distillate. The methyl esters of higher molecular weights could not be distilled without decomposition. The acids had equivalent weight varying from 334 to 442, and molecular weight varying from 567 to 659. The equiv. wt. and mol. wt. of these acids indicate the presence of polymerised dibasic and monobasic acids. The acids were gummy and probably mixtures and had appreciable acetyl value indicating the presence of hydroxy acids.

Olive Oil

Heat polymerisation of Olive Oil.—138 G. of the oil on distillation at reduced pressure gave 110 g. of the distillate (nearly 80%), 19 g. of the residue (13.7%) and 9 g. of gases (6.3%) by difference.

Composition of the Distillate.—The neutral portion of the distillate was found to consist of ketones, alcohols and hydrocarbons of varying mol. wts., accompanied by traces of a glyceride of oleic acid. In the acid portion of the distillate, palmitic and stearic acids were identified, while pelargonic acid was identified as the saturated liquid acid. Moreover, oleic acid and other low mol. wt. acids of the type obtained in niger seed oil experiments were also identified.

The Composition of the Residue.—The residue was saponified and the acids obtained were separated into liquid acids and gummy acids. The liquid acid was identified as oleic acid. The gummy acid had equiv. wt. 305 and mol. wt. 464 thus indicating the presence of polymerised acids. The presence of hydroxy acids in the polymerised acids was also indicated by their high acetyl value.

DISCUSSION

As the major part of the distillate contains free saturated and unsaturated acids, a disruption of the glycerides must be taking place. This may be due either to the hydrolysis of the oil into glycerine and the free acids, or thermal decomposition of the triglycerides into acrolein and free acids.

Acids from the Distillates

The saponifiable part in the distillate is in a small quantity and hence the triglycerides are not distilling over in any appreciable quantity. The saponifiable part is likely to be an allyl ester of a fatty acid, as the smell of allyl alcohol was frequently noticed during saponification and examination of the neutral portion.

Since low molecular weight acids, saturated as well as unsaturated, have been found in the distillate, thermal decomposition of the free acids, formed in the disruption of the triglycerides, must have been taking place to an appreciable extent.

The saturated low molecular weight acids have composition corresponding to C_7 and C_{10} . Assuming that the evidence collected is not so conclusive as to show the presence of individual acids, yet the presence of saturated low molecular weight C_7 and C_{10} acids cannot be doubted. This observation is the first of its kind. This further points out that cracking of the free fatty is followed to a certain extent by hydrogenation. Isolation of solid derivatives of these acids such as phenacyl derivatives is no doubt desirable but this necessitates the preparation of these acids in a pure condition and this was not possible as the quantities of the acids were small. The isolation of the amides and the I. V. and equivalent weights of the methyl esters give enough support for the conclusions drawn.

The low molecular weight unsaturated acids could not be identified as individual substances but oxidation experiments definitely point out the presence of unsaturated acids with equivalent weights corresponding to C_{10} acids containing one double bond, probably at the fourth carbon atom from the carboxylic group, as succinic acid was one of the oxidation products. As in the unsaturated acids originally present in the oil, the double bonds are at the 9, 10, 12 and 13th carbon atoms, a shift of the double bonds during heating must be occurring.

High molecular weight saturated acids in the distillate are only those that are present in the original oil. The formation of saturated acids with carbon atoms more than 12 during heating is entirely precluded.

It is significant that no trace of linolic acid is detected in the distillate; an appreciable quantity of oleic acid is, however, detected and its presence has been proved beyond doubt.

Along with oleic acid, small quantities of acids possessing molecular weights higher than 300 have been detected.

Neutral Portion

The identification of the neutral products is comparatively in a less satisfactory state. Unsaturated hydrocarbons, ketones and alcohols of varying molecular weights are undoubtedly present. No direct evidence for the presence of hydrocarbons could, however, be collected, but from the general properties it appears that they are present.

Residue

The residue presents a brown viscous product of a type similar to standard oils, possessing an appreciable A. V. and low I. V.

The residue can be separated into acetone-soluble and acetone-insoluble parts. The acetone-soluble part contains almost all the acids present in the oil, along with oleic acid and other high molecular weight acids, the molecular weights ranging from 300 to 567. The acetone-insoluble part resembles a gel and gives acids of high molecular weights (658).

In general, the residue contains the original solid acids, oleic acid and polymerised acids of high molecular weights. Their equivalent weights and molecular weights show that they are mixtures of monobasic and dibasic acids. All attempts to obtain homogeneous products have failed. These acids have acetyl value indicating the presence of unsaturated hydroxy acids. The stability towards oxidising agents shows that they are likely to be cyclic (Farmer, *loc. cit.*).

The main outcome of this work is the identification of low molecular weight acids. This has been done for the first time. When the other products of high molecular weight are identified the nature of these products will have to be taken into account in the final scheme of the mechanism of polymerisation.

Most of the earlier workers have tried to isolate polymerised acids in the pure condition. In this work also all such attempts have failed. Enough evidence has been obtained in the present work and also by earlier workers which proves the shifting of double bond in the heat treatment and these on polymerisation will lead to a greater number of polymerised isomers. These isomers will have closely similar properties and hence their isolation in the pure condition will be impossible because the free energy changes involved in the shifting of the double bond are likely to be very small and not very different for various positions. Bradley (*loc. cit.*) has recently reported the isolation of the pure dimer but it is very likely that it is a mixture of several isomers possessing closely allied properties. Oxidation experiments will reveal the type of the cyclic ring, *i.e.* whether it is a four membered or a six membered ring.

More chemical and physical evidence must be sought for. We are, therefore, carrying on experiments on pure simple glycerides such as triolein, trilinolin and trilinolenin.

The experimental part of this work was carried out by Messers J. D. Lagwankar and R. C. Shah.

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